

Cytotoxicity and Anti-microbial Activity of Aqueous Methanolic Extract of *Zingiber officinale* Roscoe (Zingiberaceae)

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Authors AMDEM and SAMH designed the study, wrote the protocol, managed the literature searches, performed the statistical analysis and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author GNAG managed the biological treatment. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The current study evaluates the cytotoxic Activity of aqueous methanolic extract from Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe, Zingiberaceae) against five human cancer cell lines (lung carcinoma cell line) (A549-1), Caco-2 (Colon carcinoma cell line), HepG2 (liver carcinoma cell line), Hep2-2 (larynx carcinoma cell line), PC3 (Prostate carcinoma cell line), using sulforhodamine B (SRB) assay method and study its antimicrobial activities against two species of pathogenic bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), two fungal species (*Aspergillus* and *Fusarium*) and one (*Candida albicans*) as yeast species, identification of the phenolics and flavonoids content by using HPLC.

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Place and Duration of Study: This study was conducted in the Department of Organic Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Zagazig University, Zagazig, Egypt and pharmacology animal health researcher institute, provincial Lab. Zagazig, Sharkia, Egypt. During the period between December 2015 and December 2016.

Methodology: The cytotoxic activity was assessed using sulforhodamine B (SRB) assay. Antimicrobial activity was tested by the paper disc diffusion technique. Paper chromatography and HPLC analysis were used to prove the presence of the major phenolic and flavonoid compounds.

Results: The methanolic extract of ginger gave cytotoxic activity against five human cancer cell lines the most potent cytotoxic activity which causes the death of 50% of the tumor cells With IC50 19.1 µg/ml is lung (A549-1), followed by Colon (Caco-2) with IC50 21.7 µg/ml, liver (HepG2) with IC50 22.5 µg/ml, larynx (Hep2-2) with IC50 is 29.0 µg/ml, Prostate (PC3) IC50 is 30.2 µg/ml, with SRB assay, and antimicrobial activity was determined by measuring the inhibition zone (in mm) activity against two species of pathogenic bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* with (31.7), *Pseudomonas auroginosa* with (25.3), and three species of fungi *Fusarium* with (29.3) followed by *Candida albicans* with (28.3) then *Aspergillus sp.* with (25.3). HPLC analysis identify major phenolic compounds; vanillic, ellagic, pyrogallol, salicylic, caffeic and ferulic while the major flavonoid compounds were luteolin-6-arabinose-8-glucoside, kaempferol-3-glucoside-2"-*p*-coumaroyl, apigenin-6-rhamnosyl-8-glucoside, naringin, hesperidin and acacetin as well.

Conclusion: The results in this work demonstrate that the extract of the selected medicinal plant (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe, Zingiberaceae) contains considerable amount of beneficial bioactive phenolic and flavonoid compounds which let the plant used as good candidate for novel therapeutic strategies due to its significant anticancer and antimicrobial activities.

Keywords: *Zingiber officinale*; cytotoxicity; antimicrobial activity; HPLC; phenolic, flavonoids.

1. INTRODUCTION

Natural products play an important role in health care, medicine and cure diseases for thousands of years. A lot of countries such as India, North Africans, and China use natural sources for treating various diseases [1]. Natural bioactive compounds such as tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids and phenolic compounds which are found in medicinal plants have a very important role in health care [2]. *Zingiber officinale* Roscoe is genus of plants belonging to Zingiberaceae family which include 47 genera and 1400 species such as cardamom (two main genera, Elettaria and Amour.) and turmeric (*Curium longa*). The genus, Zingier, consists of 150 species which *Z. officinale* is responsible for flavoring [3]. Ginger needs to a warm humid climate while preferring light shade [4]. So, it is grown from April to December at an optimal elevation between 300 and 900 m [5]. For more than 200 years Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe) has been used as a spice in food [6].

Zingiber officinale Roscoe contains extractable oleo resins, carbohydrates, many fats, minerals, vitamins and a potent proteolytic enzyme called zingibain. The ginger has 5-8% of oleo resins, which contribute to the sensory perception of ginger [7] and contain two main groups of chemical volatile and non-volatile pungent

compounds. Volatile oils contain more than 66 identified compounds such as zingiberene, curcumene and farnesene [8].

Non-volatile pungent compounds of ginger which responsible for hot sensation in the mouth consist of polyphenol compounds 6-gingerol and its dehydrated derivative product shogaols [9]. Beneficial of these pungent compounds is to be used in pharmaceutical industry which they contain bioactive compounds that have effects on certain physiological process.

Ginger is rich with phytochemicals like, phenolics, carotenoids, anthocyanins, procyanidins, and flavonoids. Secondary metabolites phenolic compounds which present in ginger are synthesized by the pentose phosphate, Shikimate and Phenylpropanoid Pathways [10]. They consist of thousands of compounds with different chemical structures such as carnosic acid, rosmarinic acid, caffeic acid, ferulic acid, eugenol, carnosol, thymol, carvacrol, 6-gingerol, 6-shogaol, zingerone and vanillin [11].

They have beneficial effect on human health which acts as antioxidant and antimicrobial that make them important in food and pharmaceutical industries [12].

Flavonoids are a large family of plant polyphenolic compounds which contain more than 3000 compounds represent in There are four main classes of flavonoids: catechins, flavonols, anthocyanins [13]. They have anti-hepatotoxic, anti-inflammatory and anti-ulcer activities [14] and they reduce blood lipid, glucose, and enhance human immunity [15].

It was found that some of flavonoid components such as quercetin and catechin had anticancer activities, which inhibit cancer cell growth [16].

Ginger has been used in medicine to treat a lot of diseases as cold, flu, arthritis and gastrointestinal disturbances while recent studies showed that its effect as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, hypoglycemic, chemopreventive, analgesic, antipyretic, antiemetic, anxiolytic antifungal and cardiovascular properties in both *in vivo* and *in vitro* models [17].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Plant Material

Fresh *Zingiber officinale* Roscoe (Zingiberaceae) was purchased from local hypermarket in December (2015). The plant was identified by Prof. Dr. Salwa Kawashty, department of phytochemistry and plant systematic, National Research Center (NRC), Cairo. Egypt. Voucher specimen (ZOR-2010) was deposited as a reference at the herbarium of the national research center, Cairo. Egypt.

2.2 Apparatus

UV spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-Visible-1601 spectrophotometer (Kyoto, Japan). Paper chromatography (PC) was carried out on Whatman paper No. 1 MM using the following solvent system: H₂O; 15% HOAc; BAW [n-BuOH: HOAc: H₂O (4: 1: 5, v/v/v), upper layer]. HPLC, Agilent 1100 series quaternary pump (Waldborn, Germany), connected to a photodiode array detector with variable wavelengths λ_{max} 340 and 280 nm, (Agilent Technologies, USA). Column used is Zorbax 300 SB C₁₈ (150 mm, 4.6 mm, 5 μ m).

2.3 Extraction and Isolation

Fresh plant material (3 kg) were cleaned, dried at 30 – 40°C in electric oven and crushed. Powdered material (342 gm) was defatted with

petroleum ether. The defatted residue was extracted by soaking with 96% aqu. MeOH three times extraction, each for 24 hrs with 2L) at room temperature. Methanolic extract was filtered and dried under reduced pressure at 40°C using a rotary evaporator to obtain methanol extract. The methanolic extract was shown by HPLC analysis to determine phenolic and flavonoid compounds.

2.4 HPLC Analysis

The methanolic leaf extract of *Z. officinale* was standardized by using gallic acid as a reference. A stock solution of gallic acid was prepared using 4% acetic acid in water (solvent A) and methanol (solvent B) in gradient elution. The gradient program was begun with 100% B for 50 min. 10 mg of phenolic standard was dissolved in 100 mL of methanol. Mixed stock solution of standards used for construction of the calibration curve. Standards of flavonoid aglycones were obtained from (Fluka).

2.5 Material for Biological Study

2.5.1 *In-vitro* cytotoxicity assay

It was performed at National Cancer Institute, Kasr Al Ainy Faculty of Medicine, Cairo University against Prostate (PC3), liver (HepG2), colon (Caco-2), larynx Hep2-2 and lung A549-1 by SRB assay method [18].

2.5.2 *In-vitro* antimicrobial activity studies

Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213, gram-negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, fungal species (*Aspergillus sp.* and *Fusarium*) and one species of yeast *Candida albicans* ATCC 10239 were used for antimicrobial activity studies. The lyophilized bacteria and yeast were obtained from the Standard ATCC bacteria strain and Standard ATCC fungi strain debris in (fungus Laboratory, Faculty of science, Al-Azhar University) [19].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Identification of the Phenolic Compounds

Two dimensional paper chromatography of the extract methanolic was applied on Whatman paper No.1 MM, revealed the presence of twelve

major phenolic and flavonoid compounds. The corresponding spots give positive response towards FeCl₃ spray reagent. Authentic samples of the known flavonols together with authentic samples of phenolic carboxylic acids, e.g. gallic, ellagic acids ...etc, also, commonly occurring sugars and phenolics were used for comparative paper chromatography. The samples are provided from the laboratory of phytochemistry and plant systematic, NRC, Cairo [20]. The methanolic extract was subjected to separation by HPLC [21].

Investigation of the phenolic and flavonoid compounds was done by HPLC analysis and identified by comparison with authentic samples and HPLC library, Figs. 1, 2 it found twenty one phenolic compounds matching the reference by their retention time. which they are pyrogallol; gallic; protocatechuic; catechin; catechol; chlorogenic; epicatechin; 4-hydroxy-benzoic acid; caffeine; caffeic; vanillic; *p*-coumaric; ferulic; isoferulic [22]; ellagic; α -coumaric; benzoic; 3,4,5-methoxy cinnamic; coumarin and salicylic Fig. 1 and Table 1. Identification of twenty flavonoids, luteolin-6-arabinose-8-glucoside, luteolin-6-glucosyl-8-arabinoside, Apigenin-6-rhamnosyl-8-glucoside, Naringin, Luteolin-7-glucoside, Apigenin-6-glucosyl-8-rhamnoside, Hesperidin, Rutin, Rosmarinic acid, Apigenin 7-O-neohesperidoside, Apigenin 7-glucoside, Quercetrin, Quercetin, Kaempferol-3-glucoside-

2"- *p*-coumaroyl, Naringenin, Hesperetin, Kaempferol, Rhamnetin, Apigenin, Acacetin [23] Fig. 2 and Table 2.

Table 1. Phenolic by HPLC analysis of methanolic extract of *Zingiber officinale*

	Phenolic compounds	Rt in min	mg/100 g
1.	Pyogallol	4.50	0.798
2.	Gallic	5.00	0.051
3.	Protocatechuic	9.5	0.078
4.	Catechin	11.9	0.251
5.	Catechol	12.6	0.096
6.	Chlorogenic	14.2	0.156
7.	Epicatechin	15.01	0.070
8.	4-hydroxy-benzoic acid	17.01	0.177
9.	Caffeine	18.03	0.305
10.	Caffeic	18.50	0.053
11.	Vanillic	20.10	0.124
12.	<i>p</i> -coumaric	26.00	0.096
13.	Ferulic	28.20	0.273
14.	Iso-ferrulic	29.00	0.056
15.	e-vanillic	30.00	3.189
16.	Ellagic	32.04	1.546
17.	α -coumaric	32.80	0.052
18.	Benzoic	33.02	0.501
19.	3,4,5-methoxy-cinnamic	35.00	0.159
20.	Coumarin	37.50	0.125
21.	Salicylic	40.50	0.578

Fig. 1. HPLC analysis of phenolic compounds of methanolic extract of *Zingiber officinale*

Fig. 2. HPLC analysis of flavonoid compounds of methanolic extract of *Zingiber officinale*

Table 2. HPLC analysis of flavonoid from methanolic extract of *Zingiber officinale*

Flavonoid compounds	Rt in min	mg/100 g
1. luteolin-6-arabinose-8-glucoside	1.50	59.07
2. luteolin -6-glucosyl-8-arabinoside	2.80	4.69
3. Apigenin-6-rhamnosyl-8-glucoside	5.40	18.06
4. Naringin	9.80	24.15
5. Luteolin-7-glucoside	11.90	13.84
6. Apigenin-6-glucosyl-8-rhamnoside	13.01	3.44
7. Hesperidin	13.90	15.75
8. Rutin	15.10	10.35
9. Rosmarinic acid	15.80	0.19
10. Apigenin-7-O-neohesperidoside	16.50	6.60
11. Apigenin -7-O-glucoside	18.20	12.66
12. Quercetrin	20.2	4.69
13. Quercetin	21.00	1.82
14. Kaempferol-3-glucoside-2''-p-coumaroyl	25.03	49.53
15. Naringenin	27.80	4.86
16. Hesperetin	29.60	15.42
17. Kaempferol	30.40	4.53
18. Rhamnetin	31.20	3.30
19. Apigenin	32.80	0.97
20. Acacetin	34.20	90.57

3.2 Biological Activities Results

3.2.1 Cytotoxic activity of methanolic extract of ginger against five human tumor cell lines

Methanolic extract of ginger was subjected to cytotoxic activity screening against five human tumor cell lines which are (lung carcinoma cell line) (A549-1), Caco-2 (Colon carcinoma cell line), HepG2 (liver carcinoma cell line), Hep2-2 (larynx carcinoma cell line), PC3 (Prostate carcinoma cell line), The results showed that the extract has activity against cell lines tested, most potent cytotoxic activity which causes the death of 50% of the tumor cells With IC50 19.1 µg/ml is lung (A549-1), followed by Colon (Caco-2) with IC50 21.7 µg/ml, liver (HepG2) with IC50 22.5 µg/ml, larynx (Hep2-2) with IC50 is 29.0 µg/ml, Prostate (PC3) IC50 is 30.2 µg/ml, with SRB assay, which gave a relationship between the surviving fraction and drug concentration in Fig. 3.

3.2.2 Antimicrobial activity results

The antimicrobial activity of the Ginger extract was tested by the paper disc diffusion technique. The 30 µL of the extract concentration 3 mg/mL of *Zingiber* were absorbed onto sterile 6 mm diameter filter paper discs (Schleicher and Schul, Nr 2668, Dassel, Germany). Antimicrobial activity was determined by measuring the inhibition zone (in mm) against the test organisms. All experiments were done under sterile conditions in duplicate. The standard antibacterial agent

ceftazidime (20 mg/disc) was used as a positive control for bacteria, and the standard antifungal agent nystatin (20 mg/disc) was used as the positive control for yeast. All experiments were repeated three times. DMSO was used as a negative control.

conc.µg/ml	HEP2-2 Mean	A549-1 Mean	PC3 Mean	HepG2 Mean	Caco-2 Mean
0	17.64	13.785	9.128	10.2	13.5
5	21.283	19.787	12.494	34.01	35.6
12.5	29.181	34.54	20.931	44.10	51.0
25	44.674	63.858	40.548	58.00	61.0
50	75.632	96.853	81.597	78.00	72.0

Fig. 3. % of survival fractions of five tumor cells concentration (µg/ml) of methanolic extract of ginger

Fig. 4. Antimicrobial activity for ginger extract

Results from the antimicrobial activity screening tests are shown Fig. 4. The methanolic ginger extract inhibited the growth of two microorganisms *Staphylococcus aureus* with (31.7) more than *Pseudomonas auroginosa* with (25.3) in bacterial species and for antifungal activity we found that *Fusarium* with (29.3) has more resistant than *Aspergillus* with (25.3) and *Candida albicans* with (28.3) due to presence of bioactive phenolic compound which have antibacterial and anti-fungal principles.

4. CONCLUSION

The results in this work demonstrate that the aqueous methanolic extract of ginger extract contains a beneficial bioactive phenolic and flavonoid compound which let the plant used as good candidate for novel therapeutic strategies due to its significant anticancer and antimicrobial activities.

CONSENT

It is not applicable.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

All authors hereby declare that principles of laboratory of pharmacology animal health researcher institute, provincial Lab. Zagazig, Sharkia, Egypt. All experiments have been examined and approved by the appropriate ethics committee.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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